

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY &
MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM (IJITMIS)**

ISSN 0976 – 6405(Print)

ISSN 0976 – 6413(Online)

Volume 4, Issue 3, September - December (2013), pp. 25-46

© IAEME: <http://www.iaeme.com/IJITMIS.asp>

Journal Impact Factor (2013): 5.2372 (Calculated by GIS)

DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16142924>

www.jifactor.com

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**COMPARISON OF COMPRESSION ALGORITHM FOR DNA
SEQUENCES WITH INFORMATION SECURITY USING EXACT
MATCHING OF REPEAT, REVERSE, COMPLEMENT &
PALINDROME TECHNIQUE ON DNA SEQUENCES AND APPLY ON
OTHERS ORIENTATION ALSO**

Syed Mahamud Hossein^{1,2}, Pradeep Kumar Das Mohapatra¹, Debashis De²

^{1,2}Regional Office, Directorate of Vocational Education and Training, West Bengal,
Kolaghat-721154, Purba Medinipur, India

¹Department of Microbiology, Vidyasagar University, West Bengal, Midnapur-721102, India

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering, West Bengal University of Technology,
BF-142, Sector-I, Kolkata-700064, West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

A lossless compression algorithm, for genetic sequences, based on searching individual exact Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome is reported. The compression results obtained in the algorithm show that the exact R²CP are one of the main hidden regularities in DNA sequences. The proposed DNA sequence compression algorithm is based on R²CP substring and creates online Library file. The substrings are replaced by corresponding ASCII characters starting from 33(!). The substring length depends on the user. The online library file acts as a signature. Our main objective was to reduce the compression ratio, called 1st pass compression, again compress it using any compression algorithm for better compression ratio is called 2nd pass compression and send it over the mail such that the receiver gets the DNA sequences in more compressed format. We compressed it using Huffman algorithm in 2nd pass compression. The reverse process has been applied to get the original DNA sequence. Information security is the most challenging question for protecting data from unauthorized user, this proposed method may protect the data from hackers. When a user searches for any sequence for an organism, an encrypted compressed sequence file can be sent from the data source to the user. The encrypted compressed file then can be decompressed at the client end resulting in reduced transmission time over the Internet. A encrypted compression algorithm that provides a moderately high compression ratio with encryption minimal decompression time. Compressing the genome sequences will

help to increase the efficiency of their uses. This algorithm is tested on benchmark DNA sequences and also tested on Reverse, Complement & Reverse Complement of the whole DNA sequences and artificial DNA sequences also their other orientation. The algorithm can approach a compression ratio in repeat techniques on normal sequence of 3.5940 bit/base, better than other three orientation and at the REVHUFF algorithm can approach a compression ratio of 2.143942 bit/base.

Keywords: Compression, Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome, Comparison.
Abbreviation R²CP → Repeat, Reverse, Complement and Palindrome

1. INTRODUCTION

1st pass Compression : Biological sequence compression is a useful tool to recover information from biological sequences. With more and more complete genomes of prokaryotes and eukaryotes becoming available and the completion of human genome project in the horizon, fundamental questions regarding the characteristics of these sequences arise along with their compressibility. Life represents order. The DNA sequences that encode Life is nonrandom. Naturally they should be very compressible, it is not chaotic or random [1]. There are also strong biological evidences in supporting this claim: It is well-known that DNA sequences, especially in higher eukaryotes, contain many Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome. It is also established that many essential genes (like rRNAs) have many copies. It is believed that there are only about a thousand basic protein folding patterns. Further it has been conjectured that genes duplicate themselves sometimes for evolutionary or simply for “selfish” purposes. These all concretely support that the DNA sequences should be reasonably compressible. It is well recognized that the compression of DNA sequences is a very difficult task. The DNA sequences only consist of 4 nucleotide bases {a, c, g, t}(note that t is replaced with u in the case of the RNA), 8 bits are enough to store each base. However, if one applies standard compression software such as the Unix “compress” and “compact” or the MS-DOS archive programs “pkzip” and “arj”, they all expand the file with more than 8 bits per base, although all these compression software are universal compression software. These software’s are designed for text compression [2], while the regularities in DNA sequences are much subtler. It is our purpose to study such subtleties in DNA sequences. We will present a DNA compression algorithm, based on exact matching that gives the best compression results on standard benchmark DNA sequences. However, searching for all exact Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome in a very long DNA sequence is a trivial task. These algorithms take a long time (essentially a quadratic time search or even more) in order to find approximate Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome that are optimal for compression. Simultaneously achieving high speed and best compression ratio remains to be a challenging task. Proposed DNA sequences Compression achieves a better compression ratio and runs significantly faster than any existing compression program for benchmark DNA sequences, simultaneously. Proposed algorithm consists of two phases: i) finding all exact Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome and ii) encoding exact Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome regions and non- (Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome) regions. We have developed for fast and sensitive homology search, as our exact Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome search engine. Compression of DNA sequences is a very challenging task. This can be seen by the fact that no commercial file-compression program achieves any compression on benchmark DNA sequences. Several compression algorithms specialized for DNA sequences have been

developed in earlier studies elsewhere. We will present a DNA compression algorithm, based on Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome substring and corresponding Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome substrings are place in Library file , this repeat substring creates an Library file and place ASCII character in appropriate places on source file and that gives the best compression results on standard benchmark DNA sequences & discuss details of the algorithm, provide experimental results and compares the results.

The compression ratio result in all orientation such as the Reverse, Complement and Reverse Complement the input sequences, also finds the compression ratio of equal length randomly generated artificial DNA sequence and compares the results.

If not otherwise mentioned, use lower case letters u, v , to denote finite strings over the alphabet $\{a, c, g, t\}$, $|u|$ denotes the length of u , the number of characters in u . u_i is the i -th character of u . $u_{i:j}$ is the substring of u from position i to position j . The first character of u is u_1 . Thus $u = u_{1:|u|-1}$. and $|v|$ denotes the length of v , the number of characters in v . v_i is the i -th character of v . $v_{i:j}$ is another substring of v from position i to position j . $u_{i:j}$ matches with $v_{i:j}$. The first character of v is v_1 . Thus $v = v_{1:|v|-1}$. The minimum difference between $u-v$ is of substring length. The Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome finds if $u_{i:j} = v_{i:j}$ and counts the exact maximum Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome of $u_{i:j}$. We use ϵ to denote empty string and $\epsilon=0$.

Huffman's code also fails badly on DNA sequences both in the static and adaptive model, because there are only four kind symbols in DNA sequences and the probabilities of occurrence of the symbols are not very different[3]. After 1st Compression the output DNA sequences has contain both a,t,g & c and ASCII characters, hence we have easily apply the Huffman Technique on this output sequences in 2nd pass compression.

2nd pass Compression : Huffman Coding- In computer science and information theory, Huffman coding[4-10] is an entropy encoding algorithm used for lossless data compression. The term refers to the use of a variable-length code table for encoding a source symbol (such as a character in a file) where the variable-length code table has been derived in a particular way based on the estimated probability of occurrence for each possible value of the source symbol. It was developed by David A. Huffman while he was a Ph.D. student at MIT, and published in the 1952 paper "A Method for the Construction of Minimum-Redundancy Codes." Huffman became a member of the MIT faculty upon graduation and was later the founding member of the Computer Science Department at the University of California, Santa Cruz.

Huffman coding uses a specific method for choosing the representation for each symbol, resulting in a prefix-free code (sometimes called "prefix codes") (that is, the bit string representing some particular symbol is never a prefix of the bit string representing any other symbol) that expressfes the most common characters using shorter strings of bits than are used for less common source symbols. Huffman was able to design the most efficient compression method of this type: no other mapping of individual source symbols to unique strings of bits will produce a smaller average output size when the actual symbol frequencies agree with those used to create the code. A method was later found to do this in linear time if input probabilities (also known as weights) are sorted.

For a set of symbols with a uniform probability distribution and a number of members which is a power of two, Huffman coding is equivalent to simple binary block encoding, e.g., ASCII coding. Huffman coding is such a widespread method for creating prefix-free codes that the term "Huffman code" is widely used as a synonym for "prefix-free code" even when such a code is not produced by Huffman's algorithm.

Although Huffman coding is optimal for a symbol-by-symbol coding with a known input probability distribution, its optimality can sometimes accidentally be over-stated. For example, arithmetic coding and LZW coding often have better compression capability. Both these methods can combine an arbitrary number of symbols for more efficient coding, and generally adapt to the actual input statistics, the latter of which is useful when input probabilities are not precisely known or vary significantly within the stream. You should get a tree like the following:

Fig.-1

Huffman tree generated from the exact frequencies of the text "this is an example of a Huffman tree". The frequencies and codes of each character are below. Encoding the sentence with this code requires 135 bits, not counting space for the tree.

Table-I

Char	Freq	Code
space	7	111
a	4	010
e	4	000
f	3	1101
h	2	1010
i	2	1000
m	2	0111
n	2	0010
s	2	1011
t	2	0110
l	1	11001

Table-1

We use compression & selection encryption techniques for the general purpose of sequence data delivery to the client. Existing DNA search engines do not utilise DNA sequence compression algorithms & encryption for high security for client side decompression, i.e. where a encrypted compressed DNA sequence is decrypted & decompressed at the client end for the benefit of faster transmission & information security. Because most of the existing DNA sequence compression algorithms aim for higher compression ratios or pattern revealing, rather than client side decompression, their decompression times are longer than necessary information security. This makes these compression techniques unsuitable for the “on the fly” decompression. We use a encrypted compression technique designed for client side decrypted followed by decompression in order to achieve faster sequence secure data transmission to the client.

Fig. 2

If encrypted compressed sequence data is sent from the data source to be decrypted decompressed at the client end and the decompression time along with the encrypted

compressed file transmission time is less than the transmission time for uncompressed data transfer from the source to the client, then efficiency is achieved. Fig. 2 illustrates the situation. Note that the sequence data should be kept pre-compressed within the data source. A Sequence compression algorithm with reduced decompression time and moderately high compression rate is the preferred choice for efficient sequence data delivery with faster data transmission. As our target is to minimize decompression time and high information security, we use similar compression techniques to those used in [11], based on a “Two Pass” approach, meaning, that the file is compressed followed by encryption or decrypt followed by decompressed while reading it. Unlike “four pass” algorithms there is no need to re-read the input file. Our compression technique is essentially a symbol substitution compression scheme that encodes the sequence by replacing four consecutive nucleotide sequences with ASCII characters. Our technique to find the best solution for a client side decompression technique.

2. METHODS

2.1: File Format

Now lets begin discussing file type which is text file (file extension is .txt). It contain a series of successive four base pair (a,t,g and c) and end with blank space ahead the end of file. Text file is the basic element which we consider in compression and decompression. The output file is also a text file, contains the information of both unmatched four base pair and a coded value of ASCII characters. The coded values are located in the encoded section. The coded information is written into destination file byte by byte. On the basis of ASCII code availability, we can take the input as a lower case letter of a,t,g and c.

2.2: Generating the substring from input sequence

Fig.-3 : Substring creation

From the pictorial representation of fig- I it is clear that for i^{th} substring W_i .

i , is the starting position of the substring and.

$j = (i-1) + l$, is end position of the substring; where l is the substring length i.e word size.

The substring length is less than 3 (three) has no importance in matching context therefore we consider the substring size in the range: $3 \leq l \leq n$

Therefore range for i and j are as $1 \leq i \leq n-l+1$ and $1 \leq j \leq n$ respectively.

2.3: Searching for exact matches

Consider a finite sequence s over the DNA alphabet $\{a, c, g, t\}$. An exact Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome is a substring in s that can be transformed from another substring in s with edit operations (Repeats/Reverse/Complement/Palindrome, insertion). We only encode those exact Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome that provide profits on overall compression.

This methods of compression is as below

1. Run the program and output all exact Repeats/Reverse/Complement/ Palindrome into a list s in the order of descending scores;
2. Extract a Repeats/Reverse/Complement/Palindrome r with highest score from list s , then replace all r by corresponding ASCII code into another Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome list o and place r in library file.
3. Process each Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome in s so that there's no overlap with the extracted Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome r ;
4. Goto step 2 if the highest score of Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome in s is still higher than a pre-defined threshold; otherwise exit.

2.4 : Encoding Procedures

An exact Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome can be presented as two kinds of triples. first is (l, m, p) , where l means the Repeats/Reverse/Complement/Palindrome substring length, m and p show the starting positions of two substrings in a Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome, respectively, second Replace. This operation is expressed as $(r; p; \text{char})$ which means replacing the exact Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome substring at position p by ASCII character char . In order to recover an exact Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome correctly the following information must be encoded in the output data stream:

Encoding Analysis

$m \rightarrow$

So, we can write $s = \text{atggtagtaatgtacatg} \dots \dots n$ $n > 0$ and $1 \leq i \leq n-1+1$

$p \rightarrow$

Consider the sequence defined by s , consider Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome substring store in $S[m]$ and all match Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome substring are stored in $S[p]$

After breaking the sequence(s) into substring of three bases long we can get the result as below.

So, we can get $S[m] = S[1] \dots \dots S[n-2*l+1]$ $1 \leq m \leq n-2*l+1$ and

Repeat substring are $S[p] = S[1] \dots \dots S[n-l+1]$ $1 \leq p \leq n-l+1$

If the number of substring in $S[m]$, total number of subsequence are generated by $(n-2*l+1)$ and

Number of mach Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome substring in $S[p]$, total match Repeats, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome substring are $(n-l+1)$

As per above example $s[m] \rightarrow s[1] = \text{atg}$ and so on

And $s[p] \rightarrow s[1] = \text{gta}$ and so on.

This substring method is required to reduce the complexity of the programme execution.

2.5 : Each substring matches with all other substring for finding the exact maximum match substring

Match condition occur if $S[m]=S[p]$ $p=l+1$

Step-1 : $S[1]$ match with $S[p]$ to $S[n-l+1]$ and count $S[1]$, $p++$

Step-2 :Match $S[2]$ match with $S[p]$ to $S[n-l+1]$ and count $S[2]$, $p++$, $l++$

Step-3 :This method will continue to $S[n-l+1]$

So $S[n-2*l+1]$ match with $S[p]$ to $S[n-2*l+1]$ and count $S[n-2*l+1]$

So, $S[n-2*L+1]$ repeat only one place if mach occur.

Step-4 : Store all repeat count in descending order and find all exact maximum match count

Step-5 : Replace exact maximum repeat substrings by corresponding ASCII code and place matched substrings on line library file.

Step- 6: Repeat Step-1 to step-5 excluding ASCII code

Step-7 : If the highest score of repeats in s is still higher than a pre-defined threshold; otherwise exit.

So, $n=\text{Length of the string} = \text{Total number of base pair in s} = \text{File size in byte}$

The Encoding procedure follows this rule and produces compressed output file.

$S[m]$ matches with $S[p]$ to $S[n-l+1]$,place ASCII character in the output file i^{th} position. Each matching cases the value of m is incremented by; $m=\text{number of unmatched character}+(\text{number of sub-string match} * \text{substring length} + 1)$

Otherwise $S[m]\neq S[p]$ to $S[n-l+1]$ place base pair in output files i^{th} position. If unmatched occurs , the value of m and p is incremented by one.

At the end, we can get the compressed output file o which contains the unmatched a,t,g and c and ASCII character set.

2.6 : Decoding procedure

Decoding time, first require on line Library file, which was created at the time of encoding the input file.

On this particular value, the encoded input string is decoded and produce the output original file.

Library File

$O= !""!tac!.....n_1$ where n_1 is the length of output string ($n>n_1$).

At the time of decoding each ASCII character is replaced by corresponding base pair i.e $O[M]=L[k]$ where $O[M]$ is defined by output sequence and $L[k]$ is defined by library file substring. If match occur in between $L[33]$ to $L[256]$ with $O[M]$, place ASCII equivalent substring in i^{th} places in output file. The value of m is incremented by one. If unmatched found in between $L[33]$ to $L[256]$ with $O[M]$, place base pair in i^{th} position in output file. The value of M is incremented by one. This process will continue until $M=n_1$ position will appear.

The Decoding process mentioned this rule and produce original output string.

Match is found if $o[m]=L[33]$ to $L[256]$ place ASCII character equivalent substring in i -th position. If match found, the value of m is incremented by one.

Otherwise $o[m]\neq L[33]$ to $L[256]$ place base pair in i -th position in output file. If unmatched occurs , the value of m is incremented by one.For easy implementation, characters a,t,g,c will no longer appear in pre-coded file and A,T,G,C will appear in pre-coded file.

2.7 : Flowchart

Fig-4

Fig-5

2.8: Repeat, Reverse, Complement & Palindrome for encoding (compression) algorithm & decoding(decompression) algorithms

2.8:1a: Encoding algorithm for repeated sequence using variable length

1. CH=54, CH1=32
2. Input the compression length l.
3. Input the input file name FNAME.

4. Suppose FNAME is a.txt then create a file name FLIB by appending 'lib' to the end of the FNAME like in this case alib.txt. FLIB will store the ascii characters and its corresponding word replaced its compressed file.
5. Suppose FNAME is a.txt then create a file name FCOM by appending 'com' to the end of the FNAME like in this case acom.txt. FCOM will store the compressed file.
6. Create an empty file TEMP.
7. MAX=0
8. MWORD=NULL
9. Extract a word of length L from FNAME which only consists of a, t, g, c. Check whether it exists in TEMP or not. If it exist go to step 9 else go to step 10.
10. If it is end of file go to step12 else go to step 8.
11. Append this word to TEMP. Count the number of times this word is repeated in the file. If it is greater than MAX do MWORD=this word and MAX=the count of this word.
12. If it is end of file go to step 12 else go to step 8.
13. If MAX >1 do step 13 to 17
14. CH=CH+1.if CH=a/t/g/c CH=CH+1
15. If CH=0 do CH1=CH1+1 and CH=54
16. If CH1==32 append to FLIB CH and MWORD else append to FLIB CH1 and CH and MWORD in this order.
17. Replace every word in FNAME which matches MWORD with the corresponding ascii character. Store it in FCOM.
18. Replace the content of FNAME with FCOM.
19. IF MAX>1 go to step 5
20. Remove FNAME and TEMP.

2.8:1b: Decoding algorithm for Repeated Sequence Using Variable Length

1. We accept the compressed file FCOM.
2. Suppose FCOM is 'acom.txt' we will write library file name FLIB as 'alib.txt' and original file name FNAME as 'a.txt'.
3. Read the compressed file FCOM character by character
4. If the character is a/t/g/c copy it to FNAME.
5. If the character is not a/t/g/c we will find the word matching to the character in FLIB and write that word in FNAME.
6. Do step 3 to 5 until end of file is reached.
7. Remove FCOM and FLIB
8. FNAME holds the original decompressed file.

2.8:2a: Encoding algorithm for Reverse Sequence Using Variable Length

1. CH=54, CH1=32
2. Input the compression length l.
3. Input the input file name FNAME.
4. Suppose FNAME is a.txt then create a file name FLIB by appending 'lib' to the end of the FNAME like in this case alib.txt. FLIB will store the ascii character and its corresponding word which it replaces in the compressed file.
5. Suppose FNAME is a.txt then create a file name FCOM by appending 'com' to the end of the FNAME like in this case acom.txt. FCOM will store the compressed file.
6. Create an empty file TEMP.
7. MAX=0

8. MWORD=NULL
9. Extract a word of length L from FNAME which only consists of a, t, g, c. Check whether it exist in TEMP or not. If it exist go to step 9 else go to step 10.
10. If it is end of file go to step12 else go to step 8.
11. Append this word to TEMP. Count the number of times the palindrome of the word is repeated in the file. If it is greater than MAX do MWORD=this word and MAX=the count of this word.
12. If it is end of file go to step 12 else go to step 8.
13. If MAX >1 do step 13 to 17
14. CH=CH+1.if CH=a/t/g/c CH=CH+1
15. If CH=0 do CH1=CH1+1 and CH=54
16. If CH1==32 append to FLIB CH and MWORD else append to FLIB CH1 and CH and MWORD in this order.
17. Replace every palindrome of the word in FNAME which matches MWORD with the corresponding ascii character+100. Store it in FCOM.
18. Replace the content of FNAME with FCOM.
19. IF MAX>1 go to step 5
20. Remove FNAME and TEMP.

2.8:2b: Decoding algorithm for Reverse Sequence Using Variable Length

1. We accept the compressed file FCOM.
2. Suppose FCOM is 'acom.txt' we will write library file name FLIB as 'alib.txt' and original file name FNAME as 'a.txt'.
3. Read the compressed file FCOM character by character
4. If the character is a/t/g/c copy it to FNAME.
5. If the character is not a/t/g/c we will find the word matching to the character in FLIB and write that word in FNAME.
6. Do step 3 to 5 until end of file is reached.
7. Remove FCOM and FLIB
8. FNAME holds the original decompressed file.

2.8.3a: Encoding algorithm for Complement Sequence Using Variable Length

1. CH=54, CH1=32
2. Input the compression length L.
3. Input the input file name FNAME.
4. Suppose FNAME is a.txt then create a file name FLIB by appending 'lib' to the end of the FNAME like in this case alib.txt. FLIB will store the ascii character and its corresponding word which it replaces in the compressed file.
5. Suppose FNAME is a.txt then create a file name FCOM by appending 'com' to the end of the FNAME like in this case acom.txt. FCOM will store the compressed file.
6. Create an empty file TEMP.
7. MAX=0
8. MWORD=NULL
9. Extract a word of length L from FNAME which only consists of a, t, g, c. Check whether it exist in TEMP or not. If it exist go to step 9 else go to step 10.
10. If it is end of file go to step12 else go to step 8.

11. Append this word to TEMP. Count the number of times the Complement of the word is repeated in the file. If it is greater than MAX do MWORD=this word and MAX=the count of this word.
12. If it is end of file go to step 12 else go to step 8.
13. If MAX >1 do step 13 to 17
14. CH=CH+1.if CH=a/t/g/c CH=CH+1
15. If CH=0 do CH1=CH1+1 and CH=54
16. If CH1==32 append to FLIB CH and MWORD else append to FLIB CH1 and CH and MWORD in this order.
17. Replace every Complement of the word in FNAME which matches MWORD with the corresponding ascii character+100. Store it in FCOM.
18. Replace the content of FNAME with FCOM.
19. IF MAX>1 go to step 5
20. Remove FNAME and TEMP.

2.8:3b: Decoding algorithm for Complement Sequence Using Variable Length

1. We accept the compressed file FCOM.
2. Suppose FCOM is 'acom.txt' we will write library file name FLIB as 'alib.txt' and original file name FNAME as 'a.txt'.
3. Read the compressed file FCOM character by character
4. If the character is a/t/g/c copy it to FNAME.
5. If the character is not a/t/g/c we will find the word matching to the character in FLIB and write that word in FNAME.
6. Do step 3 to 5 until end of file is reached.
7. Remove FCOM and FLIB
8. FNAME holds the original decompressed file.

2.8.4 : Encoding & decoding algorithm for Palindrome Sequence Using Variable Length

1. Enter the name of the source file.
 2. Enter the name of the destination file where the palindrome will be printed.
 3. Enter the length of the string be taken input each time from the source file.
 4. Take the first string of the specified length.
 5. Reverse the string.
 6. Check whether the source and reverse string are same or not. If same write it to output file specifying the position.
 7. If palindrome found or not take the second string of specified length starting from second character of the source file.
- Continue steps 5, 6 & 7 till the end of the file.
8. If the file is ended stop.

2.8.5 : Huffman Algorithm

The technique works by creating a binary tree of nodes. These can be stored in a regular array, the size of which depends on the number of symbols, n. A node can be either a leaf node or an internal node. Initially, all nodes are leaf nodes, which contain the symbol itself, the weight (frequency of appearance) of the symbol and optionally, a link to a parent node which makes it easy to read the code (in reverse) starting from a leaf node. Internal nodes contain symbol weight, links to two child nodes and the optional link to a parent node.

As a common convention, bit '0' represents following the left child and bit '1' represents following the right child. A finished tree has n leaf nodes and $n - 1$ internal nodes.

A linear-time* method to create a Huffman tree is to use two queues, the first one containing the initial weights (along with pointers to the associated leaves), and combined weights (along with pointers to the trees) being put in the back of the second queue. This assures that the lowest weight is always kept at the front of one of the two queues.

Creating the tree:

1. Start with as many leaves as there are symbols.
2. Enqueue all leaf nodes into the first queue (by probability in increasing order so that the least likely item is in the head of the queue).
3. While there is more than one node in the queues:
 - a) Dequeue the two nodes with the lowest weight.
 - b) Create a new internal node, with the two just-removed nodes as children (either node can be either child) and the sum of their weights as the new weight.
 - c) Enqueue the new node into the rear of the second queue.
4. The remaining node is the root node; the tree has now been generated.

2.9 : Algorithm for random string (Artificial DNA sequences) generation

Step1 \leftarrow Take the input file contain atgc sequence.

Step2 \leftarrow if(input file is not open)
 Print Unable to open the file
 Exit from the program.

 Else
 Randomize();
 Go to step 3

 End of if structure.

Step 3 \leftarrow fp=fopen("input.txt","w");

Step4 \leftarrow for i=0 to j
 fputc(A[random(4)],fp);
end of for structure

step5 \leftarrow set output file

step 6 \leftarrow stop

2.10 : Algorithm for Orientation change of Reverse, Complement and Reverse Complement of the DNA sequences

Step1 \leftarrow Enter store file.

Step2 \leftarrow Take input char by char from store file

Step 3 \leftarrow Complement the character by

```
switch(x)
{
case 'T':
return 'A';
case 'A':
return 'T';
case 'C':
return 'G';
case 'G':
return 'C';
```

Step4 ← Again take input char by char from source
step5 ← do reverse the input string and store
step 6 ← do complement of this reverse string using step 3
step 7 ← get 3 output txt file
step 8 ← stop

2.11 : Algorithm for File size calculation

Step1 ← Enter store file.
Step2 ← Take input char by char from store file
Step 3 ← open(infile, O_CREAT);
step 4 ← File size in byte
step 5 ← stop

2.12 : Algorithm for file mapping

Step1 : frame_size=LENGTH(String_1);
Step2 : Repeat step 3 to 5 while String_1 is NULL.
Step3 : Index=MISMATCH-INDEX(String_1,String_2).
Step4 : IF Index>Length(String_1)-1 then goto step 6.
Step5 : IF Index=Length(String_1)-1
 then String_1=NULL.
 ELSE
 String_1=SUBSTRING(String_1,(Index+1)).
 String_2=SUBSTRING(String_2,(Index+1)).
Step6 : Error_no=Error_no + 1.
Step7 : Percentage = ((Frame_size-Error_no)/Frame_size)*100.
Step8 : Return Percentage.

3. ALGORITHM EVALUATION

3.1: Accuracy

As to the DNA sequence storage, accuracy must be taken firstly in that even a single base mutation, insertion & deletion would result in huge change of phenotype as we see in the sickle cell anemia. It is not tolerable that any mistake exists either in compression or in decompression. Although not yet proved mathematically, it could be inferred from R²CP techniques that our algorithm is accurate, since every base arrangement uniquely corresponds to an ASCII character.

3.2: Efficiency

We can see that the internal R²CP algorithm can compress original file from substring length (l) into 1 character for any DNA segment, and destination file uses less ASCII character to represent successive DNA bases than source file.

3.3: Space Occupation

Our algorithm reads characters from source file and writes them immediately into destination file. It costs very small memory space to store only a few characters. The space occupation is in constant level. In our experiments, the OS has no swap partition. All performance can be done in main memory which is only 512 MB on our PC.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This software is used on standard benchmark data [12]. For testing purpose we use eight types of data. These tests are performed on a computer whose CPU is Intel P-IV 3.0 GHz core 2 duo(1024FSB), Intel 946 original mother board, IGB DDR2 Hynix, 160GB SATA HDD Segate. Since these programs to implement the technique have been written originally in the C++ language[13-14], (Windows XP platform, and TC compiler) it is possible to run in other microcomputers with small changes (depending on platform and Compiler used). The programs runs on the IBM personal computer, requires 512K, without additional hardware except for disk drives and printer.

The definition of the compression ratio[15] is defined as $(|O|/|I|)$, where $|I|$ is number of bases in the input DNA sequence and $|O|$ is the length (number of bits) of the output sequence. The normal sequence result & their orientation result is presented in Table-II, artificial result presented in Table-III and Table-IV present our algorithms REVHUFF result

Table-II

Sequence Size		Cellular DNA Sequences																
		Normal Sequences				Reverse Sequences				Complement Sequences				Reverse Complement Sequences				
		Sequence Name	Base pair File size	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Repeat Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Reverse Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Complement Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Palindrome Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Repeat Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Reverse Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Complement Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Palindrome Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Repeat Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Reverse Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Complement Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Palindrome Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Repeat Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Reverse Techniques	Compression ratio (bits/byte) using Complement Techniques
Sub string Size 3	atatsgs	9647	3.6678	4.2964	4.1057	3.8436	3.6794	4.2948	4.0460	3.9083	3.6662	4.2831	4.1057	3.8436	3.6794	4.2500	4.0460	3.9083
	atef1a23	6022	3.6453	4.3600	4.0411	3.8711	3.6612	4.2856	4.0571	3.8764	3.6426	4.3228	4.0411	3.8711	3.6612	4.3361	4.0571	3.8764
	atrdnaf	10014	3.5805	4.1829	3.9912	3.8106	3.5821	4.1829	4.0311	3.8122	3.5789	4.1925	3.9912	3.8106	3.5821	4.1957	4.0311	3.8122
	atrdnai	5287	3.5362	4.0900	3.8630	3.7662	3.5150	4.0870	3.8600	3.7329	3.5331	4.0234	3.8630	3.7662	3.5150	4.0234	3.7283	3.7329
	cdk07e12	58949	3.5600	4.0752	4.0179	3.7970	3.5657	4.0749	4.0177	3.7910	3.5598	4.0559	4.0179	3.7970	3.5657	4.0814	4.0177	3.7910
	hsg6pdgen	52173	3.6026	4.2892	4.1064	3.8562	3.5980	4.2889	4.1012	3.8691	3.6023	4.2760	4.1064	3.8562	3.5980	4.2760	4.1012	3.8691
	mmzp3g	10833	3.5882	3.8423	4.0269	3.8408	3.6104	3.8319	4.0166	3.8319	3.5868	3.8408	4.0269	3.8408	3.6104	3.8334	4.0166	3.8319
	xlxf512	19338	3.5718	3.7687	3.9540	3.7679	3.5751	3.7861	3.9698	3.7861	3.571	3.7679	3.9540	3.7679	3.5751	3.7861	3.9698	3.7861
Sub string Size 4	atatsgs	9647	3.3071	3.5484	3.5691	3.5468	3.2905	3.5517	3.5492	3.5517	3.3054	3.5468	3.5691	3.5468	3.2905	3.5517	3.5492	3.5517
	atef1a23	6022	3.3158	3.5788	3.6758	3.5762	3.3131	3.5682	3.6678	3.5682	3.3131	3.5762	3.6758	3.5762	3.3131	3.5682	3.6678	3.5682
	atrdnaf	10014	3.3137	3.5550	3.5717	3.5534	3.3169	3.5630	3.6397	3.5614	3.3121	3.5550	3.5717	3.5534	3.3169	3.5630	3.6397	3.5614
	atrdnai	5287	3.3682	3.7177	3.7420	3.7147	3.3833	3.5785	3.7283	3.5785	3.3652	3.7147	3.7420	3.7147	3.3833	3.5785	3.7283	3.5785
	cdk07e12	58949	3.2010	3.4726	3.5200	3.4512	3.2128	3.4319	3.5250	3.4756	3.2007	3.4724	3.4857	3.4724	3.2125	3.4756	3.5250	3.4266
	hsg6pdgen	52173	3.1725	3.4103	3.5074	3.4572	3.1890	3.4726	3.5058	3.4726	3.1722	3.4342	3.5216	3.4572	3.1795	3.4187	3.5058	3.4726
	mmzp3g	10833	3.3313	3.4878	3.5380	3.4863	3.3320	3.5366	3.6023	3.5366	3.3298	3.4863	3.5380	3.4863	3.3320	3.5380	3.6023	3.5366
	xlxf512	19338	3.1556	3.4162	3.4278	3.4154	3.1560	3.3571	3.4286	3.3778	3.1548	3.4154	3.4278	3.4154	3.1560	3.3778	3.4179	3.3778

Graph-I-1 (Fig-6)

Graph -I-2 (Fig-7)

Graph-I-3 (Fig-8)

Graph-I-3 (Fig-8)

Table-III

Sequence Size	Sequence Name	Base pair/ File size	Artificial sequences																
			Normal Sequences				Reverse Sequences				Complement Sequences				Reverse Complement Sequences				
			Compression ratio (bits /base) using Repeat	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Reverse	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Complement Techniques	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Palindrome Techniques	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Repeat	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Reverse	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Complement Techniques	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Palindrome Techniques	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Repeat	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Reverse	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Complement Techniques	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Palindrome Techniques	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Repeat	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Reverse	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Complement Techniques	Compression ratio (bits /base) using Palindrome Techniques	
Sub string Size 3	atatsgs	9647	3.6496	3.6363	3.6496	3.6363	4.3213	4.3196	4.3196	4.3097	4.0344	4.0261	4.0344	4.0261	3.9183	3.9100	3.9183	3.9100	
	atefla23	6022	3.6346	3.6320	3.6320	3.6320	4.2935	4.2803	4.2803	4.2882	4.0650	4.0385	4.0677	4.0385	3.8897	3.8950	3.8897	3.8950	
	atrdnaf	10014	3.6269	3.6157	3.6253	3.6157	4.2500	4.2484	4.2484	4.2612	4.0487	4.0599	4.0487	4.0599	3.8665	3.9225	3.8665	3.9225	
	atrdnai	5287	3.6542	3.6481	3.6512	3.6481	4.3018	4.2988	4.2988	4.2837	4.0506	4.0627	4.0506	4.0627	3.9084	3.9084	3.9084	3.9084	
	celk07e12	58949	3.6268	3.6255	3.6265	3.6255	4.2828	4.2826	4.2826	4.1580	4.0730	4.0730	4.0730	4.0730	3.9001	3.9053	3.9001	3.9053	
	hsg6pdgen	52173	3.6375	0.3632	0.3637	0.3632	4.2969	4.2966	4.2966	4.2944	4.106	4.1110	4.1061	4.1110	3.9295	3.9243	3.9295	3.9243	
	mmzp3g	10833	3.6385	3.6399	3.6385	3.6399	4.2662	4.2544	4.9928	4.3031	4.0801	4.0727	4.0801	4.0727	3.8984	6.9978	3.8984	3.8925	
	xlxfg512	19338	3.6239	3.6247	3.6231	3.6247	4.2684	4.2676	4.2676	4.2337	4.0426	4.0608	4.0610	4.0608	3.9185	2.1805	3.9185	3.9201	
	Sub string Size 4	atatsgs	9647	3.2822	3.2905	3.2806	3.2905	3.6048	3.5766	3.5766	3.6031	3.6330	3.6562	3.6330	3.6562				
		atefla23	6022	3.3995	3.3689	3.3968	3.3689	3.6027	3.6160	3.6160	3.6001	3.6878	3.6240	3.6878	3.6240	3.6001	3.6160	3.6001	3.6160
atrdnaf		10014	3.3185	3.3145	3.3169	3.3145	3.5965	3.6357	3.6357	3.5949	3.6165	3.6325	3.6165	3.6325	3.5949	3.6357	3.5949	3.6357	
atrdnai		5287	3.3501	3.3788	3.3470	3.3788	3.6587	3.6466	3.6466	3.6557	3.7283	3.6920	3.7283	3.6920	3.6557	3.6466	3.6557	3.6466	
celk07e12		58949	3.2144	3.2121	3.2330	3.2303	3.4993	3.5579	3.4960	0.7818	3.5778	3.5788	3.5778	3.5788	3.5591	3.5579	3.5591	3.5579	
hsg6pdgen		52173	3.2203	3.2214	4.1906	3.2379	3.4920	3.4966	3.4966	3.5090	3.5638	3.5958	3.5638	3.5958	3.5377	3.4735	3.5377	3.5475	
mmzp3g		10833	3.3091	3.2692	3.3091	3.2692	3.5897	3.5971	3.5971	3.5513	3.6510	3.6170	3.6510	3.6170	3.5882	3.5971	3.5513	3.5971	
xlxfg512		19338	3.2760	3.2677	3.2752	3.2677	3.5772	3.5221	3.5221	3.5763	3.5751	3.5772	3.5751	3.5772	3.5763	3.5685	3.5763	3.5685	

Graph-II-1 (Fig-9)

Graph-II-2 (Gig-10)

Graph-II-3 (Fig-11)

Graph-II-4 (Fig-12)

However, our algorithms doesn't compress sequences as much as others for many of the cases in the compression ratio but it provide high information security.

Table-IV

Normal Sequence							
Sequence Name	Base pair/ File size	1 st Pass data Compression			Our Compression algorithm 'REVHUFF'		
		Reduce file size Byte	Lib. File size	Compression ratio (bits /base)	Reduce file size Byte	Lib. File size	Compression ratio (bits /base)
atatsgs	9647	4423	354	3.6678	2580	227	2.139525
atef1a23	6022	2744	366	3.6453	1626	213	2.16008
atrndaf	10014	4482	378	3.5805	2733	239	2.183343
atrndai	5287	2337	294	3.5362	1389	184	2.101759
celk07e12	58949	26233	384	3.5600	15705	246	2.131334
hsg6pdgen	52173	23495	384	3.6026	14180	245	2.174305
mmzp3g	10833	4859	360	3.5882	2902	230	2.143081
xlxfg512	19338	8634	372	3.5718	5120	239	2.118109

Graph-III(Fig-13)

In order to compare the overall performance, we conducted further studies involving sending actual sequence files of varying sizes (without compression) to measure the calculated time (T_c) needed for the transmission from the source to the destination. Then we compressed those files using both compression & encryption algorithms. The total time T , defined as the sum of the encryption compressed file transmission time (T_{ec}) plus the client side decompression time (T_{dd}), is measured by both these methods.

5. RESULT DISCUSSION

The experiments results in sub-sequences length 3 & 4, conclude that internal R^2CP matching patten are same but compression rate are slightly different to each other in all type of cellular sources, this is shown by Table-II & III , compression pattern are symmetric nature in all types of cellular DNA sequences, shown in Graph-I-1,Graph I-2, Graph I-3 & Graph I-4, the better Compression rate is found in Repeat technique. Library file plays a key role in finding similarities or regularities in DNA sequences. The experiments results in sub-sequences length of 3 & 4 bases , conclude that internal R^2CP matching patten are different in all type of artificial sources, shown in Table-III & compression pattern are asymmetric nature in all types of artificial DNA sequences Graph-II-1, Graph-II-2, Graph-II-3 and Graph-II-4. Final result of our algorithm is shown in Table-IV and Graph-II is in symmetric nature. Output file contain ASCII character with unmatched a,t,g and c, it can provide information security which is very important for data protection over transmission point of view. This techniques provide the high security to protect nucleotide sequence in a particular source. Our algorithm is very useful in database storing. You can keep sequences as records in database instead of maintaining them as files. By just using the exact R^2CP , users can obtain original sequences in a time that can't be felt.

6. CONCLUSION

These DNA compression software whose key idea is internal R^2CP . This Repeat technique compression algorithm gives a good model for compressing DNA sequences that reveals the true characteristics of DNA sequences. The compression results of R^2CP DNA sequences also indicate that our method is more effective than many others. This method is able to detect more regularities in DNA sequences, such as mutation and crossover, and achieve the best compression results by using this observation. This method is fails to achieve

higher compression ratio than others standard method, but it has provide very high information security.

Important observation are :

- a) R²CP substring length vary from 2 to 5 and no sufficient match found in case the substring length becoming six or more.
- b) The substring length three is highly repeated than substring length of four and five i.e substring length of three is highly compressible over substring length of four and five.
- c) Normal sequence is highly compressible than reverse, complement and reverse complement sequences.
- d) Cellular DNA sequences compression rate are homogeneous in nature because all the cellular DNA sequences are comes into the same family where as artificial DNA sequences compression rate are heterogeneous in nature in all time in all data sets.
- e) The cellular DNA sequence encode amino acid/protein that why sub-sequence of repeat/reverse/palindrome/genetic complement are found in the original sequence, more exact match are found in the repeat search method, other orientation the exact match are found in less number over repeat method.
- f) Life represents order. It is not chaotic or random [1]. Our result are showing that cellular DNA sequence are reasonable compressible in any orientation (cellular DNA sequence, reverse sequence, complement sequence and reverse complement sequence) result is homogeneous in nature and showing graph also where as artificially(random sting) generated sting of same length compression rate is heterogeneous in nature and showing in graph.
- g) One and two pass algorithm is lossless where as three pass algorithm is lossy.
- h) This technique are apply on corresponding other orientation of cellular DNA sequences like Reverse, Complement & reverse complement of DNA sequence, the better result found on normal i.e cellular DNA sequence performance.
- i) This algorithm provide the better data security than other methods. If we use security directly on the cellular DNA sequence, we are getting very low label security because DNA sequence contain only four bases, anyone can hack the data by trial error methods where as our result show that after compression it has created four separate file first one is compress data contain 256 (ASCII) different characters, so it provide strong security label second file is library life, which is also contains more than four characters. At the time of transmission if two files are transmit one by one it is very hard to hack the data, these techniques has also provide data secure.

The ratio of decompression time to original transmission time of the uncompressed sequence file (T_{dd} / T_c), reduces with increasing file size. This means our client side decompression technique with our algorithm is a better choice for larger sequence files. Our client side decompression technique can be implemented by a genome search agent and decompression time can be estimated by two empirical equations according to our experiments.

Our algorithms combines moderate compression with reduced decompression time to achieve the best performance for client side sequence delivery compared with existing techniques. Its linearity in decompression time and close linearity in compression time make it an effective compression tool for commercial usage. Given, for a particular connection speed, the efficiency achieved using our algorithm, this compression technique is recommended for transmission of queried sequence files.

Table-V

Sequence	Base pair/File size	GZIP	BZIP2	Our Compression algorithm 'REVHUFF'
atatsgs	9647	2.1702	2.15	2.139525
atef1a23	6022	2.0379	2.15	2.16008
atrdsnaf	10014	2.2784	2.15	2.183343
atrdsnai	5287	1.8846	1.96	2.101759
celk07e12	58949			2.131334
hsg6pdgen	52173	2.2444	2.07	2.174305
mmzp3g	10833	2.3225	2.13	2.143081
xlxfg512	19338	1.8310	1.80	2.118109

We compared the results of 'REVHUFF' Compress to the best DNA compression algorithms GZIP & BZIP2 Table V shows the compression ratios (the number of bits per base) of these algorithms on standard benchmark sequences. 'REVHUFF' *Compress* achieves the best average compression ratio.

7. Future work

We are develop to further research on as combination of two sub sequences such as reverse-repeat, repeat-palindrome etc and combination of three sub sequences such as repeat-reverse-palindrome etc and compare to each other. Also we try to reduce the time complexity.

8. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Above all, author are grateful to all our colleagues for their valuable suggestion, moral support, interest and constructive criticism of this study. The author offer special thanks to Ph.D guides for helping in carrying out the research work also like to thank our PCs.

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ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Syed Mahamud Hossein: Post Graduate student for Doctor Degree for Computer Science in Vidyasagar University. He received his post graduate degree in Computer Applications from Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathawada University [M.Sc.-C.A.], Nanded and Master of Engineering in Information Technology [M.E.-I.T.] from West Bengal University of Technology, Kolkata. He has worked as the Senior Lecturer in Haldia Institute of Technology, Haldia, Lecturer on contract basis in Panskura Banamali College, Panskura and Lecturer in Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar Polytechnic, Govt. of West Bengal, Jgargram. Now he is working as a District Officer, Regional Office, Kolaghat, Directorate of Vocational Educational & Training, West Bengal since 2010. His research interests includes Bioinformatics, Compression Techniques & cryptography, Design and Analysis of Algorithms & Development of Software Tools. He is a member of professional societies like Computer Society of India (life member) & Indian Science Congress Association (life member)